

Beauty of Magic Squares: 3888-Multiple Order Bordered Magic Squares of Order 144 - Part 1

Inder J. Taneja¹

The work is also available at author's site:
<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=18662>

Abstract

*This paper presents a systematic construction of **multiple order bordered magic squares** at orders 12, 20, 30, 42, 56, 72, 90, 108 and 144. (for a full structural summary). Unlike classical block-wise bordered magic squares, which are built as multiples of a single block size, the structures explored here incorporate successive borders drawn from magic squares of **different** orders — specifically orders 3 through 9 — each contributing a distinct structural layer. To bring order 144, order 9 is used twice to bring 108, and finally the order 18 is applied over 108 to bring 144. The magic squares orders are considered as 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 9 and 18. In some cases, **even-order borders** consist of **equal-sum**, while **odd-order borders** consist of **different-sum** magic squares. In some cases, the even orders are also considered with different magic sums. The combinatorial multiplicity of border types at each level yields a hierarchy of distinct configurations.*

Keywords: magic squares, bordered magic squares, **pandiagonal** magic squares, multiple order borders, combinatorial enumeration, recreational mathematics.

¹Formerly, Professor of Mathematics, Federal University of Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, SC, Brazil (1978-2012).
Also worked at Delhi University, India (1976-1978).
E-mail: ijtaneja@gmail.com;
Web-sites: <http://inderjtaneja.com>; <http://numbers-magic.com>;
Twitter: @IJTANEJA; **Instagram:** @crazynumbers.

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1 Introduction

A **magic square** of order n is an arrangement of n^2 distinct integers in an $n \times n$ grid such that the sums of each row, each column, and both main diagonals are equal. This common value is called the **magic constant** (or magic sum), usually denoted S . For a magic square containing the consecutive integers $1, 2, \dots, n^2$, the magic constant is

$$S = \frac{n(n^2 + 1)}{2}. \tag{1}$$

Magic squares have fascinated mathematicians, artists, and philosophers for millennia, appearing in ancient texts. Two constructions are central to the present work.

Definition 1.1 (Bordered magic square). *A magic square is said to be **bordered** if the removal of any outermost border of cells leaves a smaller magic square. All entries are consecutive integers.*

Definition 1.2 (Block-wise bordered magic square). *A magic square is **block-wise bordered** if each border layer is not a single cell wide but is composed of smaller magic squares used as building blocks.*

During past years author [4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10] worked with **block-wise** magic squares from orders 12 to 47. Author [11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16] also worked with **bordered** magic squares. The study on **bordered** magic squares is extended to **block-bordered** magic squares [17, 18, 19]. This is specially done for the magic squares of orders p and $2p$, where p is a prime number. This study is still extended to **block-wise bordered** magic squares [20, 21, 22, 23]. Some connection with Pythagorean triples and area-representations are also made [25, 26, 27, 28, 29]. The main property of **bordered** magic squares is that if we remove external borders, still we get **sub-bordered** magic squares, i.e., each layer in itself lead us to magic squares. In many cases, the properties of **bordered** magic square are separated by **even** and **odd** orders magic squares. In many cases, we get good properties for the **even** order **bordered** magic squares. In some cases, we have to use fractional numbers to reach minimum perfect square sum of entries. For more study on **bordered** magic squares refer H. White's web-site [3].

The idea of bordered magic squares is already discussed by H. White's web-site [3] where the borders are of **single digits**. Borders multiples of even numbers starting from order 4 are done extensively by author [25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30].

1.1 Summary of Bordered Magic Squares

1.1.1 Odd Numbers Multiples

- **Single Digit:** Bordered magic squares based on single digit [11, 12, 3].
- **Three Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 3 [30].
- **Five Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 5 [32].
- **Seven Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 7 [34].
- **Nine Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 9 [36].
- **Eleven Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 11 [38].
- **Thirteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 13 [40].
- **Fifteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 15 [42].
- **Seventeen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 17 [44].
- **Nineteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 19 [46].

1.1.2 Even Numbers Multiples

- **Two Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic rectangles multiples of 2 [74, 75, 76, 77, 77, 78, 79].
- **Four Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 4 [25, 31].
- **Six Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 6 [26, 33].
- **Eight Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 8 [27, 35].
- **Ten Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 10 [28, 37].
- **Twelve Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 12 [29, 39].
- **Fourteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 14 [41].
- **Sixteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 16 [43].
- **Eighteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 18 [45].
- **Twenty Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 20 [47].

The advantage in working with even number multiples is that we can work with equal sums blocks of magic squares.

The aim of this work is to bring multiple order **bordered** magic squares of orders 20, 30, 42, 56, 72, 90, 108 and 144. Let see below how it is done.

See below the details of above multiple order bordered magic square.

• **0 Border: Different sums magic squares of order 3**

1. Initially, we have a magic square of order 12 formed by different sums magic squares of order 3.

• **1st Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 4**

1. In this case, we have considered two types of magic squares of order 4.

(a) The first is **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4.

(b) The second is formed by two equal sums magic sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 resulting in a magic square of order 4. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 20

• **2nd Border: Different sums magic squares of order 5**

1. In this case, we have considered three different types of magic squares of order 5.

(a) The first is **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 5.

(b) The second is **cornered** magic square of order 5, where there are two **equal sums magic rectangles** of order 2×3 and a magic square of order 3 at the upper-left corner.

(c) The third is **single-layer bordered** magic square with magic square of order 3 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 30

• **3rd Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 6**

1. In this case also we have considered three different types of magic squares of order 6.

(a) The first is normal magic square of order 6.

(b) The second is **cornered** magic square of order 6, where there is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 at the upper-left corner with two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 .

(c) The third one is **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 6 with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 42

• **4th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 7.**

1. In this case, we have considered 5 different types of magic squares of order 7.

(a) The first is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 7.

(b) The second is **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 7, where there is a magic square of order 3 in the middle and 4 equal sums **magic rectangles** of orders 2×3 .

(c) The third is a **cornered** magic square of order 7 composed of another **cornered** magic square of order 5 with magic squares of order 3 at the upper-left corner. Two equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×3 and two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×5 .

(d) The forth is also a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 7 with magic square of order 3 in the middle. Also there are four equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×5 . This type of magic squares we call as **cyclic-double-layer** magic square of order 7.

(e) The fifth is a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 7, where there is a magic square of order 3 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 56.

• **5th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 8**

1. In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 8.

(a) The first is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 formed by four equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4.

(b) The second is a **cornered** magic square of order 8, where there is again a **cornered** magic square of order 6 with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×4 and 2×6 are of equal sums in each case.

(c) The third is a **double-layer bordered** magic square with **pandiagonal** with a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. It has 2 equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×8 and two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 .

(d) The forth is also a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 8 with a magic square of order 4 in the middle. This magic square of order 4 is again composed two equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 . The magic square of order 4 also have four equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×6 . Since it is formed by only **strips** of equal width, we call it a **striped** magic square of order 8.

(e) The fifth one is four equal sums magic squares of order 4, where each magic square of order 4 is formed by two equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 . Since it is formed by only magic rectangles of equal width it is known as **striped** magic square.

(f) The sixth one is **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 8 having a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic square of order 72.

• **6th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 9**

1. In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 9.

(a) The first is composed of 9 **semi-magic** squares of order 3 resulting in a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 9.

(b) The second is a cornered magic square, where magic squares of orders 7 and 5 are also **cornered** magic squares at the upper-left corner having magic square of order 3.

(c) The third is **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 9 having **cornered** magic square of order 5 in the middle. Two **magic rectangles** of orders 2×3 and two **magic rectangles** of orders 2×5 are of equal sums in each case.

(d) The forth is again a **double-layer bordered** with **single-layer** bordered magic square of order 5 at the middle. The external border is composed of 2 **magic rectangles** of order 2×9 and two **magic rectangles** of order 2×5 . Both are of equal sums in each case. In the middle there is a magic square of order 3.

(e) The fifth is again a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 9 with external bordered as 4 equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×7 . In the middle there is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5. This kind of magic square we call as **cyclic-type double-layer bordered** magic square of order 9

(f) The sixth is a normal **single-layer** bordered magic square of order 9 having magic square of order 3 in the middle.

• **7th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 9**

1. In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 9.

- (a) The first is a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 9 embedded with a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 7. It contains 4 equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×3 with magic square of order 3 in the middle.
- (b) The second is again a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 9 embedded with a **cornered** magic square of order 7. It contains again a **cornered** magic square of order 5 in the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of order 2×3 and of order 2×5 are of equal sums in each case.
- (c) The third is again a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 9 embedded with a **cyclic-double-layer bordered** magic square of order 7. It contains 4 equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×5 with magic square of order 3 in the middle.
- (d) The fourth is again a **cornered** magic square of order 9 having a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 7 embedded with **cornered** magic square of order 5. The **magic rectangles** of orders 2×3 and 2×7 are of equal sums in each case.
- (e) The fifth is again a **cornered** magic square of order 9 having a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 7 in the upper-left corner. The four **magic rectangles** of orders 2×3 are of equal sums. Also the two magic rectangles of orders 2×7 are of equal sums.
- (f) The sixth is a **corner-type** magic square of order 9 formed by 2 equal sums **magic rectangles** of orders 2×9 and 2 equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×5 having **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 in upper-left corner. It is modified form of the **fifth-type** magic square.

• **8th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 18**

1. In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 18.

- (a) The first is a composed of 9 equal sums magic squares of order 6. Out of them five are **single-layer** magic square with pandiagonal magic square of order 4 in the inner parts. The other four magic squares of order 6 are **corner-type** magic square with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the corner. There are total 9 equal-sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4.
- (b) The second magic square of order 18 is composed of external border of order 4 and internal as magic square of order 10. The external border of order 4 is composed of 4 equal-sums **pandiagonal** sums magic squares of order 4 and 4 bordered magic rectangles of order 4×10 . The inner part is a magic square of order 10 formed by **single-layer** magic square of order 10 with 4 equal-sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4.
- (c) The third magic square is order 18 is composed of external border of order 3 formed different sums magic squares of order 3. The internal part is a magic square of order 12. It is again formed by **bordered** magic rectangle of order 10×12 and two single-rows of order 1×12 .

- (d) The fourth magic square of order 18 is composed of external border of order 4 and internal magic square of order 10. The external bordered is **cyclic-type** 4 equal sums magic rectangles of order 4×12 . The internal part is a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 10. It has a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle.
- (e) The fifth is composed of **double-layer cyclic-type** 4 equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×16 as an external border. The internal part is a magic square of order 16 formed by two magic squares of orders 6 and 8 and two **single-layer bordered** magic rectangles of order 6×10 .
- (f) The sixth is a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 18 with a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle.

Below summarises the construction levels.

- **0 Border: Different sums magic squares of order 3**
 - Initially, we have a magic square of order 12 formed by different sums magic squares of order 3.
- **1st Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 4**
 - In this case we have considered two different types of magic squares of order 4. Combining with magic square of order 12 we have **2-different types** of magic squares of order 20.
- **2nd Border: Different sums magic squares of order 5**
 - In this case, we have considered 3-different types of magic squares of order 5. Combining with 3 magic squares of order 20 we have **6-different types** of magic squares of order 20.
- **3rd Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 6**
 - In this case also we have considered 3-different types of magic squares of order 6. Combining with 6 magic squares of order 30 we have **18-different types** of magic squares of order 42.
- **4th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 7.**
 - In this case, we have considered 5-different ways of magic squares of order 7. Combining with 18 magic squares of order 42 we have **90-different types** of magic squares of order 56.
- **5th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 8**
 - In this case we have considered 6 different types of magic squares. Combining with 90 magic squares of order 56 we have **540-different types** of magic squares of order 72.
- **6th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 9**
 - In this case we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 9. Combining with 540 magic squares of order 72 we have $6 \times 540 = 3240$, i.e., **3240-different types** of magic squares of order 90.

- **7th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 9**

- In this case we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 9. Combining with 3240 magic squares of order 90 we have $6 \times 3240 = 19940$, i.e., **19940-different types** of magic squares of order 108. Since the number 19940 is too high to handle, we worked with only 648 magic squares of order 90. This gives us $6 \times 648 = 3888$ magic squares of order 108.

- **8th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 18**

- In this case we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 18. Combining with 19940 magic squares of order 108 we have $6 \times 19940 = 116640$, i.e., **116640-different types** of magic squares of order 144. Since the number 116640 is too high to handle, we worked with only 648 magic squares of order 108. This gives us $6 \times 648 = 3888$ magic squares of order 144.

The total count at each level equals the product of all variant counts up to that level:

$$N_{\text{ord. 144}} = 1(3) \times 2(4) \times 3(5) \times 3(6) \times 5(7) \times 6(8) \times 6(9) \times 6(9) \times 6(18) = 116640 \quad (2)$$

More details of last border i.e., 8th border of magic squares of order 18 are given section below.

2 Multiple Order Bordered Magic Squares of Order 144

In order to get **bordered magic squares** of order 144, we shall use the following 6-different types of magic squares of order 18 over the magic square of order 108 as an upper border magic squares resulting in magic squares of order 144.

18	Inder J. Taneja				https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA				2925		
17	310	11	312	317	8	302	300	21	306	22	24	281	44	53	274	47	276	2925	
12	311	18	309	315	10	20	35	292	29	294	305	287	38	48	275	54	273	2925	
314	13	308	15	323	2	26	30	293	36	291	299	279	46	278	49	272	51	2925	
307	16	313	14	9	316	28	296	31	290	33	297	45	280	271	52	277	50	2925	
4	3	324	318	6	320	298	289	34	295	32	27	42	284	282	288	40	39	2925	
321	322	1	7	5	319	301	25	304	19	303	23	41	283	43	37	285	286	2925	
194	192	129	198	130	132	176	174	147	180	148	150	266	264	57	270	58	60	2925	
128	143	184	137	186	197	146	161	166	155	168	179	56	71	256	65	258	269	2925	
134	138	185	144	183	191	152	156	167	162	165	173	62	66	257	72	255	263	2925	
136	188	139	182	141	189	154	170	157	164	159	171	64	260	67	254	69	261	2925	
190	181	142	187	140	135	172	163	160	169	158	153	262	253	70	259	68	63	2925	
193	133	196	127	195	131	175	151	178	145	177	149	265	61	268	55	267	59	2925	
111	112	216	210	114	212	230	228	93	234	94	96	78	248	246	252	75	76	2925	
214	213	109	115	113	211	92	107	220	101	222	233	77	247	79	73	250	249	2925	
125	202	119	204	117	208	98	102	221	108	219	227	81	244	89	238	83	240	2925	
120	203	126	201	207	118	100	224	103	218	105	225	251	74	84	239	90	237	2925	
206	121	200	123	215	110	226	217	106	223	104	99	243	82	242	85	236	87	2925	
199	124	205	122	209	116	229	97	232	91	231	95	245	80	235	88	241	86	2925	
1	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

18	Inder J. Taneja				https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA				2925		
87	240	81	242	7	313	316	6	8	321	10	2	322	320	95	232	89	234	2925	
82	241	88	239	324	307	20	16	311	13	310	17	306	1	90	233	96	231	2925	
244	83	238	85	314	18	305	309	14	312	15	308	19	11	236	91	230	93	2925	
237	86	243	84	5	12	9	319	317	4	315	323	3	318	229	94	235	92	2925	
67	264	254	65	203	196	198	210	130	128	126	116	114	204	27	304	294	25	2925	
253	247	78	72	125	137	190	131	192	145	182	139	184	200	293	287	38	32	2925	
256	80	245	69	123	132	191	138	189	140	183	146	181	202	296	40	285	29	2925	
66	76	249	259	119	194	133	188	135	186	141	180	143	206	26	36	289	299	2925	
68	251	74	257	113	187	136	193	134	179	144	185	142	212	28	291	34	297	2925	
261	73	252	64	201	153	174	147	176	161	166	155	168	124	301	33	292	24	2925	
70	250	75	255	205	148	175	154	173	156	167	162	165	120	30	290	35	295	2925	
62	77	248	263	207	178	149	172	151	170	157	164	159	118	22	37	288	303	2925	
262	246	79	63	208	171	152	177	150	163	160	169	158	117	302	286	39	23	2925	
260	61	71	258	121	129	127	115	195	197	199	209	211	122	300	21	31	298	2925	
111	216	105	218	47	273	276	46	48	281	50	42	282	280	103	224	97	226	2925	
106	217	112	215	284	267	60	56	271	53	270	57	266	41	98	225	104	223	2925	
220	107	214	109	274	58	265	269	54	272	55	268	59	51	228	99	222	101	2925	
213	110	219	108	45	52	49	279	277	44	275	283	43	278	221	102	227	100	2925	
2	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

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274	279	272	247	252	245	85	90	83	67	72	65	13	18	11	283	288	281	2925
273	275	277	246	248	250	84	86	88	66	68	70	12	14	16	282	284	286	2925
278	271	276	251	244	249	89	82	87	71	64	69	17	10	15	287	280	285	2925
58	63	56	151	162	173	154	155	169	168	158	159	165	164	172	265	270	263	2925
57	59	61	98	225	96	219	92	230	218	101	222	110	108	231	264	266	268	2925
62	55	60	97	210	126	204	208	201	205	125	112	111	123	228	269	262	267	2925
4	9	2	226	212	138	130	198	190	129	133	193	189	113	99	319	324	317	2925
3	5	7	105	206	194	181	141	143	145	186	179	131	119	220	318	320	322	2925
8	1	6	232	114	128	140	148	175	178	149	185	197	211	93	323	316	321	2925
292	297	290	216	116	188	183	177	150	147	176	142	137	209	109	31	36	29	2925
291	293	295	102	122	191	146	184	182	180	139	144	134	203	223	30	32	34	2925
296	289	294	221	118	136	195	127	135	196	192	132	187	207	104	35	28	33	2925
301	306	299	234	202	199	121	117	124	120	200	213	214	115	91	22	27	20	2925
300	302	304	94	100	229	106	233	95	107	224	103	215	217	227	21	23	25	2925
305	298	303	174	163	152	171	170	156	157	167	166	160	161	153	26	19	24	2925
40	45	38	76	81	74	238	243	236	256	261	254	310	315	308	49	54	47	2925
39	41	43	75	77	79	237	239	241	255	257	259	309	311	313	48	50	52	2925
44	37	42	80	73	78	242	235	240	260	253	258	314	307	312	53	46	51	2925
3	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

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13	6	315	313	317	310	1	3	16	5	321	323	14	318	41	286	288	35	2925	
314	297	22	300	23	26	307	301	20	17	304	306	27	11	34	45	280	291	2925	
316	28	303	25	302	299	18	24	305	308	21	19	298	9	287	50	275	38	2925	
7	319	10	12	8	15	324	322	309	320	4	2	311	312	285	272	53	40	2925	
97	230	232	91	203	198	128	196	130	126	116	210	114	204	289	51	274	36	2925	
90	213	112	235	125	138	132	192	194	181	143	183	137	200	282	54	271	43	2925	
231	106	219	94	201	135	176	174	147	180	148	150	190	124	29	279	46	296	2925	
229	216	109	96	123	136	146	161	166	155	168	179	189	202	31	273	52	294	2925	
233	222	103	92	208	141	152	156	167	162	165	173	184	117	44	48	277	281	2925	
226	111	214	99	113	191	154	170	157	164	159	171	134	212	33	269	56	292	2925	
85	223	102	240	205	186	172	163	160	169	158	153	139	120	293	276	49	32	2925	
87	217	108	238	119	185	175	151	178	145	177	149	140	206	295	278	47	30	2925	
100	104	221	225	207	188	193	133	131	144	182	142	187	118	42	55	270	283	2925	
89	101	224	236	121	127	197	129	195	199	209	115	211	122	290	39	37	284	2925	
237	220	105	88	69	62	259	257	261	254	57	59	72	61	265	267	70	262	2925	
239	107	218	86	258	241	78	244	83	82	251	245	76	73	248	79	250	67	2925	
98	110	215	227	260	84	247	81	242	243	74	80	249	252	77	246	75	65	2925	
234	95	93	228	63	263	66	68	64	71	268	266	253	264	60	58	255	256	2925	
4	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

18	Inder J. Taneja		https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/							https://numbers-magic.com/							@IJTANEJA	2925	
	1	3	323	321	320	6	318	8	9	315	11	313	312	14	310	16	17	308	2925
	324	322	2	4	5	319	7	317	316	10	314	12	13	311	15	309	19	306	2925
	49	276	72	66	258	260	247	77	249	71	126	204	119	200	123	203	307	18	2925
	275	50	69	242	240	81	246	82	84	256	207	194	196	127	133	118	305	20	2925
	51	274	70	80	95	232	89	234	245	255	116	132	135	190	193	209	304	21	2925
	273	52	75	86	90	233	96	231	239	250	205	134	188	137	191	120	22	303	2925
	272	53	257	88	236	91	230	93	237	68	115	195	138	187	130	210	302	23	2925
	54	271	252	238	229	94	235	92	87	73	208	128	189	136	197	117	24	301	2925
	270	55	251	241	85	244	79	243	83	74	201	192	129	198	131	124	25	300	2925
	56	269	254	259	67	65	78	248	76	253	122	121	206	125	202	199	299	26	2925
	57	268	150	183	140	181	139	184	177	146	224	222	99	228	100	102	27	298	2925
	267	58	180	170	156	171	158	152	168	145	98	113	214	107	216	227	297	28	2925
	59	266	143	172	159	164	165	162	153	182	104	108	215	114	213	221	296	29	2925
	265	60	176	151	166	161	160	163	174	149	106	218	109	212	111	219	30	295	2925
	264	61	147	157	169	154	167	173	155	178	220	211	112	217	110	105	294	31	2925
	262	63	179	142	185	144	186	141	148	175	223	103	226	97	225	101	32	293	2925
	64	261	33	291	35	289	288	38	286	40	41	283	43	281	280	278	48	46	2925
	62	263	292	34	290	36	37	287	39	285	284	42	282	44	45	47	277	279	2925
5	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

18	Inder J. Taneja			https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/			https://numbers-magic.com/			@IJTANEJA			2925						
307	292	294	296	298	318	320	322	34	32	30	28	26	8	6	4	2	308	2925	
25	275	262	264	266	285	287	289	64	62	60	58	41	39	37	35	276	300	2925	
23	57	247	236	238	240	256	258	90	88	86	84	70	68	66	248	268	302	2925	
21	55	83	223	214	216	231	233	112	110	108	95	93	91	224	242	270	304	2925	
19	52	81	107	203	196	198	210	130	128	126	116	114	204	218	244	273	306	2925	
15	51	79	104	125	138	132	192	194	181	143	183	137	200	221	246	274	310	2925	
13	46	75	103	123	135	176	174	147	180	148	150	190	202	222	250	279	312	2925	
11	44	73	98	119	136	146	161	166	155	168	179	189	206	227	252	281	314	2925	
1	42	65	96	113	141	152	156	167	162	165	173	184	212	229	260	283	324	2925	
301	269	243	219	201	191	154	170	157	164	159	171	134	124	106	82	56	24	2925	
303	271	245	220	205	186	172	163	160	169	158	153	139	120	105	80	54	22	2925	
305	272	249	225	207	185	175	151	178	145	177	149	140	118	100	76	53	20	2925	
309	277	251	226	208	188	193	133	131	144	182	142	187	117	99	74	48	16	2925	
311	278	253	228	121	129	127	115	195	197	199	209	211	122	97	72	47	14	2925	
313	280	254	101	111	109	94	92	213	215	217	230	232	234	102	71	45	12	2925	
315	282	77	89	87	85	69	67	235	237	239	241	255	257	259	78	43	10	2925	
316	49	63	61	59	40	38	36	261	263	265	267	284	286	288	290	50	9	2925	
17	33	31	29	27	7	5	3	291	293	295	297	299	317	319	321	323	18	2925	
6	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

See the details:

- In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 18.
 1. The first is a composed of 9 equal sums magic squares of order 6. Out of them five are **single-layer** magic square with pandigonal magic square of order 4 in the inner parts. The other four magic squares of order 6 are **corner-type** magic square with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the corner. There are total 9 equal-sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4.
 2. The second magic square of order 18 is composed of external border of order 4 and internal as magic square of order 10. The external border of order 4 is composed of 4 equal-sums **pandiagonal** sums magic squares of order 4 and 4 bordered magic rectangles of order 4×10 . The inner part is a magic square of order 10 formed by **single-layer** magic square of order 10 with 4 equal-sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4.
 3. The third magic square is order 18 is composed of external border of order 3 formed different sums magic squares of order 3. The internal part is a magic square of order 12. It is again formed by **bordered** magic rectangle of order 10×12 and two single-rows of order 1×12 .

4. The forth magic square of order 18 is composed of external border of order 4 and internal magic square of order 10. The external bordered is **cyclic-type** 4 equal sums magic rectangles of order 4×12 . The internal part a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 10. It has a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle.
5. The fifth is composed of **double-layer cyclic-type** 4 equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×16 . as an external border. The internal part is a magic square of order 16 formed by two magic squares of orders 6 and 8 and two **single-layer bordered** magic rectangles of order 6×10 .
6. The sixth is a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 18 with a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle.

Combining with 3240 magic squares of order 90 we have $6 \times 3240 = 19940$, i.e., **19940-different types** of magic squares of order 108. Since this number is too high, we worked with 648 magic squares of order 108, resulting in 3888 magic square of order 144. Below are few examples, with figures.

Above there are only few examples, but there are 3888 magic squares of order 144 composed of magic squares orders 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 9 and 18. More details are in an **excel files** attached with the work.

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